

Data Capturing and Processing System

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(A Case Study of the Nigeria Stock Exchange, Ilorin Branch)

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Abstract - The purpose of this project is to suggest how stock processing can be better handle to produce more meaningful and quick report. The objectives of the study are provision for automatic validation record and check balances for automated record keeping system, better record keeping for members in areas of personal records with numerous staff and proper files. The problems encounter are: Increase in clerical operation, problem of internal communication, reduce relations with outside groups, clashes and improper documentation and reducing efficiency. The problem of Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) system can be solved by creating computer based system with programs written and completed to meet the desired objectives and satisfactory result that would further improve the services and management of the stock exchange system in Nigeria. A high level language called Visual Basic programming was used. It is a complex relation database management package.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the questions anyone might be tempted to ask is why stock exchange system rather than capital money marketing system or the related activities of money capital to stock exchange system? Is there a difference or are they related due to the capital exchange in financial aspect.

To this there are numbers of different perceptions of what the two items means can be measured according to their diversities to firm ground.

According to Frank J. Fabozzi, Steve V. Mam, Moorad Choudhry. The global money markets wiley and Finance, Wily and sons (2002), A money market can be defined as a component of the financial market for assets involved in short term borrowing, lending buying and selling with original maturites of one year or less. Trading in money market is done over the counter and is wholesale. On the other hand According to Ndamusa S.A (2004) defined capital market as the collection of financial institutions set up for the mobilization of medium or long term loans. It is a market for long term instrument which include; market and mortgages of loans, that is, the market for mobilization and utilization of long term funds for development

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Stock exchange as a form of exchange which provide services of stock exchanges brokers and traders to buy or sell blocks, bonds and other securities. Stock exchange also provide facileness and other finical instrument and capital events including the payment of income and dividends. Lemke and Lins (Thomson West, 2013-2014 ed).

1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim and objectives of the computerized study are as follows;

- The system facilities better data storage and retrieval
- Provides improvement for better stock exchange record efficiency
- Provision for automatic validation record check balances for automated record keeping system.
- Accuracy for needed input and speedy manipulation of results.
- Complete eradication of numerous files and relief of management staff in keeping hundreds of files.
- Better record keeping for members in areas of personal records with numerous staff and proper files.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The basic significance of the study is listed below:

- The design of computerized system that will handle entire problem identified.
- The implementation of the design system.
- The study of present system of the designed system.
- Identification of the limitations and future consideration of the new system

1.4 METHODOLOGY

In the computerization of the stock exchange market system must be well considered.

In stock exchange system, the system needs well developed software (program) that will manipulate the process of buying and selling of securities between members i.e. Brokers and Jobbers. The stock exchange system is computerized to handle various application, which range from individual to group firms. The software program is divided into various classes i.e. a subprogram handling personal record, stock and bonds record, shares and related securities records. This will be later explained in the later chapter for better understanding.

1.5 SCOPE AND LIMITATION

The computerization of stock exchange system basically provided efficiency and effectiveness in stock exchange system, which enhances accuracy, reliability speedy records and

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record keeping of the system in areas of computerization. Hence, the scope of the study is to provide a complete software documentation which will be employed in the management of the exchange system.

The implementation of a computerization stock exchange system is limited in areas of complete application in various stock exchange companies.

Also, its limitation will be affected by improvement in software abilities and upgrading or producing of various version of software (WINDOWS VERSIONS) in recent times. Hence, the computerization system will need upgrading according to the hardware and software configuration.

1.6 ORGANISATION OF REPORT

Chapter one contains introduction, aims and objectives, significance of the study, methodology, scope, and limitation of the project, organization of report.

Chapter two contains the literature review, historical background, technical terms and computerization of stock exchange.

Chapter three contains analysis of the existing system, description of advantages of the proposed system.

Chapter four contains the Design, implementation and Development of the system.

Chapter five contains the summary, experienced gained, recommendations and the conclusion.

1.7 TECHNICAL TERMS

- i. **STOCK EXCHANGE:** is a firm where various types of securities (bond, stock and share) are trade openly and easily.
- ii. **BROKERS:** These are membership of the exchange which act on behalf of investors and buy and sell securities on their behalf as their agents.
- iii. **DEALING NUMBERS:** These are people who have granted the license to buy and sell shares on trading floors of the exchange on behalf of the investing public.
- iv. **DIVIDEND:** Payment of share of profit, to shareholders in a business company, or assets creditors (e.g. of an investment company) or to a policy holder in a mutual insurance company, to pay a dividend of 10mpercent, dividend warrant, order on a bank to pay a dividend.
- v. **PREFERENCE STOCK:** Stock on which dividend payment must be made before profits are distributed to holders of ordinary stock.
- vi. **JOBBERS:** They specialized in a particular type of stock and shares and act as wholesale or middleman

- vii. **PRICING:** Prices of new issues are determined by issuing houses/ stock brokers which on the secondary market prices are made stock broker only.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF THE CASE STUDY

The Nigerian Stock Exchange was started as the Lagos Stock Exchange in 1960 as an organ of Nigerian Capital Market. Originally known as the Lagos Stock Exchange at inception. It was reconstituted into the Nigeria Stock Exchange in December, 1977 with staff strength of 54 peoples, with branches established in some of the major commercial cities of the country. Each branch as a trading floor. The branch in Lagos was opened in 1961, Onitsha in 1990, Ibadan in 1990, Abuja in 1999, Yola in 2002 and Ilorin 2008. Lagos branch is the head of the exchange.

The exchange started operations in 1991 with 19 securities listed on the exchange in trading. Today there are 283 securities listed on the exchange in two market segments, first tier market is for companies that have at least 25% of their equity capital available to the public among other requirements, while the second tier market is for upcoming small and medium enterprises, which have 100% of their equity capital available to the market.

In order to ensure fairness in the dealings on the floor of the exchange, a supervisory body known as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) was established in 1979. The trading days and time on the Lagos Exchange are Monday – Friday, 11:00 to 13:00, charges include a 3% commission fee. As at of December 31, 2013. It has about 200 listed companies with a total market capitalization of about ₦12.88 trillion (\$80.8 billion).

2.2 STOCK EXCHANGE

A stock exchange system is a firm where various types of securities (bonds, stock and shares) are traded on openly and easily.

To be précised securities in a stock exchange system are documentary evidence of ownership or entitlement to claim upon the asset of the issuing organization, which may be a business firm, government organization and government institution. Securities rarely fixed value before they are traded in the stock exchange at value which is sub-objectively determined by those buying and selling them. Securities came in various forms i.e. in bonds, shares or stock. Bonds are securities issued by the government or companies as debt, usually at a fixed interest rate and are detachable company for the claiming of the interest.

A share is used for paying capital, while stock are issued capital of a company or partner security. The stock exist to provide a market for every large numbers of investment, any of such securities could be sold or brought in a stock exchange system. The entire system has the fast of Oderinde Kehinde Rachael

distribution, marketing and issuing securities, other parties may assist the firm in performing this task by acting as agents e.g. Merchant bank, Insurance Companies Etc.

2.3 MEMBERS IN STOCK EXCHANGE

There are two types of membership in stock exchange known as:

- i. Ordinary Members
- ii. Dealing Members
 - Ordinary members are people who have in accordance with the article of the exchange taken up. Five chequer (50k each) of issued shares capital of the exchange and has been admitted the register of member.
 - Dealing members are people who have been granted to license to buy and sell shares on the trading floors of the exchange on behalf of the investing public.

Members of the exchange consist of brokers and jobbers.

Brokers and Jobbers

Brokers act on behalf of investors and buy and sell securities on their behalf as their agents. Jobbers are not permitted to deal with the public and may only transact business with other jobbers and with brokers.

Jobbers specialized in certain securities of the market such as the share on company, breweries or banks. Brokers make their living from commissions earned by acting on behalf of clients.

2.4 THE ROLE OF STOCK EXCHANGE

The role of stock exchange provides a market in a wide range of trade securities, the stock exchange is thought of as both a primary and secondary market. A primary market is where the issue of new securities raises new funds, while a secondary market is where trade takes place in already issued securities.

The stock exchange is only a secondary market as securities are initially sold on the stock exchange trading floor by the issuer; instead they are also sold on the floor of the exchange provide that the stock exchange council have signified their approval that the stock exchange council have signified their approval by quoting the security on their list. Views on how successfully the stock exchange as an institution as the symbol of capitalism. The stock exchange as an institution has been involved by time and perfected by experience. It is the citadel of capital on the temple of value, the axle on which the whole financial structure of the capitalism system turns etc.

2.5 STOCK EXCHANGE MANAGEMENT

The management system is an effective one capable of manipulating the report provided by the firm in a stock exchange from where the management is effective. The profit here has income over a long period of time. The stock exchange firm depends on the quality of the factors to access and evaluate. It has a marketed influence never the less on the level of price of the equality. Whereas asset value and past earnings is a guide to the firm value an equality share, it is the ability of management to recognize changing circumstances and to amount policy to taking account of their charges. Aspect of managing the system is by dividing payments and share holders meeting.

2.6 COMPUTERISATION OF STOCK EXCHANGE

Data communication involves the movement of data or information between electronics devices which could include the computer system or satellite system etc. This should be distinguished from the more general term telecommunication involving the transmission of any signals between remote systems. Such signals could be data, or television or simple telephone (voice) message.

Efficient data communication is critical for today's business within a particular site, employee need to talk to each other, send message, receive replies, disseminate information and circulate updates. Indeed it is important in circumstances that different companies or businesses have similar efficient intercommunication method available. For example a company may require immediate feedback from variety securities and general information on stock market prices e.g. ICC shone watch provides an on-line database for subscribers to obtain information for share holders in UK companies.

In all cases, whether within a company or between companies and individual, data communication can play an important role in making the business more efficient.

The ability for diverse computer system is to be linked together in order to end and transmit data is called connectivity. Without connectivity, computer would not be able to communicate with each other. The stock exchange has gone a long trend and this is where the computer is fit in or found its way into the financial information considering the stock exchange which includes numerous information (database) that involve stock, bond and securities and possible setback involved. Some of the problems solved by computerizing the stock exchange system include:

1. Accuracy for need input and speed, manipulation of results
2. Complete eradication of numerous files and relief of management staff in keeping hundred of files
3. Provision of automobiles validation record and check balances for automated record keeping

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4. Provision improvement for better stock exchange record efficiently etc. all the affirmation provide or enhance:
 - a. Accuracy
 - b. Reliability, speed and record keeping of the system. Hence, the scope of the study is to provide complex software document which will be employed in the management of the stock exchange system.

III. PROJECT METHODOLOGY

3.1 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

The method of data collection used in this project is "Investigation Method". This is the act of searching and locating a specific term, which is needed for a particular research.

The methods are as follows:

1. We make investigation base on the material given to us in the place of our study.
2. Enquires are also made on the internet. I.e. Google concerning the history, function, role and operation of stock exchange in Nigeria.
3. The officials of stock exchange in Ilorin branch were also consulted for necessary information needed
4. More so enquires are also made by the guideline given to us by our supervisor in order to guide us in writing this project.

3.2 ANALYSIS OF DATA AND THE EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system of the stock exchange is a system which is set up to manipulate marketing scene between buyer and sellers of securities in form of shares stocks and bonds. Normally the stock exchange is been regulated by the securities and stock exchange market commission to complete by the activities of Nigeria Enterprises which is done to ensure that the correct proportion to share in foreign companies were transferred to Nigeria market in accordance to the promotion act.

There are various basic procedures which are to be undergone in ensuring proper movement of securities from the upper most level to the down level. Basically, the management procedure of the stock exchange system is being regulated by the exchange commission inaugurate a primary market, where new funds are raised by the issue of new securities. This is done to ensure proper regulation of the stock exchange because the stock exchange is a secondary market where trade takes place in already issued securities.

Firstly, stock is been sold to institute (or individual in year cases) who are then free to resell the n to the floor of the exchange, provided that the stock exchange council here signified their approval by quoting the securities on their official list.

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When an investor decides to buy from a particular institution or from dealing members i.e. jobbers, the investors is in most cases represented by brokers (who buys and sells shares on behalf of the investors). A certain certificate is issued to the investors in accordance with the number of shares brought included on the form and certificate is the name of the company, type of share, holders name, and signature and contracts constitutions.

Also, in a stock exchange, there are various requirements for securities stakes, this involves if the company is a liability company, a share holder, a partnership company, sole proprietorship etc.

Institutions such as merchant banks which are members of the issuing association buys a block of shares from other institution (or existing share holders) and after then to the general public at a fixed price. This offer is advertised in the press i.e. on various magazines in which the prospective of the issue is published together with an application form which the investors can fill in and send off with has cheque to the bank or other institution handling the issue.

The stock exchange is completely or finally analyze at the end of year return or payment or payment of dividend and to the share holders, which are mostly declared at the annual general meeting along with other routine null the management of the system is assisted by the shareholder meeting hold annually.

3.3 PROBLEMS OF THE EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system as already state is operated manually irrespective of the number of buyers and sellers of securities, hence, it is been associated with lots of problems which developed from the manual operation. The problems are explained below:

- I. **Increase in clerical operation:** Due to the rate of awareness, there is increase in clerical operations which invariably leads to increase in more staff and in turn may increase pressure in office space and equipment needed to support clerical activities.
- II. **Problem of internal communication:** It is common to find organization structures in which separate departments duplicate functions or produce conflicting information. Usually, these conditions arise because local systems are been put in place. In other words, proper internal communication between shareholders and the subscribing company is very much important In case of information transfer, this is so because the shareholders and (companies or institution) issuing houses here to be link in case of an abstract increase or decrease in shares.
- III. **Reduce relations with outside groups:** The normal operation of the stock exchange is a problem to the development of the system because the speed and accuracy with which transactions are processed is very low compared to when new computing equipment is used which is more reliable and generally acceptable to the general public.

- IV. **Clashes and improper documentation:** In the sense that due to the manual operation of the system, problems of inadequate interval communication cause shareholders or issuing house to allocate improper shares or stock to more than an institution or in some cases more clashes in the exchange market; also documentation of the system files. Forms and certificates are unreliable due to the normal handling of the system.
- V. **Reducing efficiency:** The stock exchange market major objective is to bring efficiency into the stock market i.e. institutions and investors are to bring savings into the stock market which otherwise might have gone elsewhere in the international market but this cannot be achieved to above highlighted problems, hence, the size and strength of the market is not efficiently managed. This problem as contributed in to no small measure to the retardation of the stock exchange.

3.4 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed stock exchange is a system designed to achieve its aim and objective of the existing system i.e. the primary of the stock exchange market. In achieving this, lots of basically incorporation is involved to boost them throughout and efficiency of the stock exchange system.

The basic feature / quality of the proposed system are the computerization of the system. Computerization of the existing system is very necessary so as to facilitate better operation of the system in the next millennium and to do away with the problems encountered in the manual operations of the systems.

3.5 ADVANTAGES OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

- I. **STOCK MARKET EFFICIENCY:** The proposed system strengthens the size and efficiency of the market because of the qualified features of computerization. This is enhanced due to the accuracy of output result, speed of processing, reliability of output data records.
- II. **REDUCTION IN CLERICAL:** The proposed aimed at reducing clerical cost by taking over many of the functions performed by clerical staff, which in turn may reduce pressure in office space and equipment needed especially reduction in paper work and file keeping. This facilitates is to better quality control, functioning in mentioning error report, management report and documents generated by any computer system.
- III. **IMPROVED INTERNAL COMMUNICATION:** Internal communication is greatly improved due to introduction of networking facility in the proposed system whereby issuing house and shareholders are connected via their computer terminals. This enables better relationship with the public generally because this facilitates better communication both internally and outside the group.
- IV. **REDUCE INTEREST CHARGES:** System which improves the control of operation, may serve to minimize stocks share are bonds. The interest charge associated with capital to

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finance production and stock holding may therefore be reduced. Implements in the efficient of daily securities routine may similarly improve cash flow. Those are all inside and important benefits from a new system.

- V. Improved quality of information.
- VI. Improved relationship with outside groups.

3.6 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION METHODOLOGIES

In the computerization of the stock exchange market system both the software subsystem and the hardware subsystem must be well considered.

In stock exchange system, the system needs well developed software (program) that will manipulate the process of buying and selling of securities between members i.e. brokers and jobbers. The stock exchange system is computerized to handle various applications, which ranges from individual to group firms. The software program is divided into various classes i.e. a subprogram handling personal, record, stock and bonds, record, shares and related securities records.

IV. DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION AND DOCUMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

4.1 DESIGN OF THE SYSTEM

System design is perhaps the designing phase which is the most satisfying aspect of this project work because it ranges over the functions that have to be performed by the proposed system. The stage is composed of several steps, which provides the understanding and procedural details necessary for implementing the system recommendation in the study. The phase step involves.

- i. Output design
- ii. Input design
- iii. File/database design
- iv. Procedure design

4.1.1 OUTPUT DESIGN

The step in system, majority focus on how the design is going to look like at the output level. This is to ensure or determine the elements of data required in output, their structure, and degree of accuracy and frequency of production in analyzing the detail description of the system, the computerization stock exchange system is made of five major modules that are developed into subprograms. They include the flowing routine creation of file, editing area, report generation, deleting data, listing records. The operation to be carried out any print in time depends on the user's response to the system prompt. A sample of this is given below:

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Client Name	Address	Sex	Company	Stock Type	Unit Bought	Total
ayinde ruqayat	poly gate	Male	firstown ventures	Shared	2	20
Olagunju Moses Tayo	Ara	Male	COnerstone venture	Stocks	4	80
Oderinde Kenny Rachael	Adejumobi	Female	Prime venture	Stocks	4	0
Oloruntoba Samson Segun	No 12 Aduralere Street	Male	Coca Cola B	Shared	3000	17400
Oloruntoba Samson S.	No 12 Aduralere Street	Male	Coca Cola B	Shared	3000	17400

Figure 4.1

The above figure is an output screen display of how the main menu will look like; when an option is being selected this choosing option is then displayed with its own submenu e.t.c. Note: that the input majority determines the type of output. The other output will be attached to the sample output.

4.1.2 INPUT DESIGN

This is referred to the file structure in which these element can be stored or generated to produce the required output. Also the input design is the process of converting user originated input to a computer based formats. It consist of specification and procedure for data and these steps are necessary to put transaction into a usable form for processing and data entry.

Input specification basically, describes the manner in which data enter describes the manner in which data enter the system at five main guidelines i.e.

- a) Controlling the amount of input require
- b) Avoiding delay
- c) Controlling the step simple
- d) Avoiding extra steps

In this study processing occurs to the main menu stated in the output design above, hence data entry is done via the keyboard in which the stock exchange data are keyed into the file with the field names e.g. in a serial form:

- i. Customer code – customer number e.g in serial form
- ii. Customer name
- iii. Type of share i.e type of stock bought or sold
- iv. Data entry
- v. Address
- vi. Quality of stock
- vii. Price shares i.e the price at which each shares was bought or sold (50k #)
- viii.Amount i.e amount of money paid for the quality.

WELCOME TO STOCKARAGE [Client Profile]

THE Nigerian STOCK EXCHANGE *Live from the Trading Floor*

Client Profile Creation

Clients Name: Surname First

Address:

Phone No: Sex:

Issuing Company:

Stock Type: Unit Bought:

Unit Price: Total Worth: N/A

Transaction Date:

Passport: Upload

DESIGNED BY GROUP 113: SUPERVISED BY: MR MURITALA

Create Refresh Close

Figure 4.2

4.1.3 FILE/DATABASE DESIGN

File design emphasis the analysis of the file before imputing of data into the system i.e. before processing the file description show the necessary information need to enhance smooth running of the system to obtain the adequate result. It shows the format in which the data are into the computer to obtain its required test.

Normally, the file will in some parts proper recording of the raw data or fact, which the other parts will contain the processing data i.e. information. File organization in the stock exchange system is organized so as to enhance proper documentation and easy implementation of file organization and program execution.

Most importantly the records, storage in the files are records which are managed according to the records in the input design. This include customers name, code, address, type of share, quality of stock, price of stock, data of entry, money and the necessary records needed for system implementation of the stock exchange system.

4.1.4 PROCEDURE DESIGN

In the stock exchange record each of the file is define and the following is taken into consideration.

- i. Name of field
- ii. Description
- iii. Medium in which it resides
- iv. Field length

The file is illustrated in a tubular form below showing the name of customers, quantity of stock, price and data.

4.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

This aspect basically refers to the step taken in executing the proposed system (most especially in implementation of the program) the processing stage has an intermediary between the input and output stage, hence it requires proper skill by a computer expert in programming.

The processing stage is a very crucial stage due to its complexity in programming. As explained in the output design. The program is a complex program made up of 6 modules to enhance simplicity; this module is carefully analyzed in the main menu, which is boldly displayed on the screen during execution.

The choice is made by the computer user to enter which aspect he/she is going to execute i.e. either data entry, editing stock data, report generating, deleting stock data, listing stock data or exit to DOS prompt.

The problem of bond will determine which modules to execute. The module highlighted will give its own submenu and output of command or data is done, entered and executed.

PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE USED WITH REASON

The programming write up for this project is a very complex, comprehensive and well organized program that requires skills combined with simplicity of the program. Hence various considerations were taken for the choice of programming language.

Finally, a high level language called visual basic programming was chosen, it is a complex relation database management package. Characteristics which attest its choice as the programming language for the study is listed below;

- a. A user friendly
- b. Screen design
- c. Posses good memory without program
- d. Process good memory allocation
- e. Allow viewing of database files in different ways e.g. view list, edit and browse e.t.c

Database possesses some qualities or merits which make it facilities to user, such as:

1. It has screen and program generator
2. It aids modular programming
3. It fastens program development it has wide variety of a application
4. It has wide variety of a application
5. It provide menu – driven facility for it data
6. It is English – like and therefore facilitates easy coding and debugging
7. It ensures faster storage and retrieval of information
8. It also has provision for Local Area Network (LAN)

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The above qualities are merits which made visual Basic a programming language more preferred than other programming language.

In running the program you must install a Dbase package on the hard disk and follow the following steps:

1. Boot the computer system to DOS prompt e.g. C:/>
2. Type path C:/> Dbase
3. Insert the diskette containing the program files into drive i.e. A,B
4. Type of stock
5. Press enter to display main menu
6. Select option among list display in the main menu.

HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SUPPORT

4.2.1 HARDWARE SUPPORT

Data communication enables computers to be linked together in order to send and receive data based system. The range of hardware required includes a device for sending data/ a device for receiving and the appropriate communication link for the transmission between two remote computers.

A telephone line can be used as the communication link insuch case, a modern is required to connect the computer to each end into communication link. Communication software is installed in each computer to enable the link to be achieved.

MODEM: This is used to enables the computer to be linked into the telephone system. The computer is connected to the modem which is in turn connected into the telephone system. Modems are required for the use with some telephone system since the signals used are in compatible. Computer work on digital (on/off) where as some of the telephone system used signals in a wave from (so called analogue signals). The modem converts digital from the computer into analogue signals carried over the telephone system. The signal is received into a second computer through another modem which converts the signals into digital format. Fig 4.3 illustrate two computers linked using modems at each end. It should be noted that with the use of digital telephone system, modem are not necessary.

The procedure whereby signals are converted from digital to analogue is called MODULATION and conversion back from analogue to digital is DEMODULATION.

Figure 4.3

TYPES OF MODEM

- I. Internal: Residue inside the C.P.U
- II. External: Separate box outside the C.P.U
- III. A crustic couple: for attaching to the telephone receive rather than direct into the telephone line.

In extending our scope on the proper data communication which also be sending or connecting system in different location any country A and country B in order to share data abs=d resources. A computer network contained within a restricted area (such as a single office or within a few miles) connecting computer and other devices spread over long distance (such as linking says in different country) i.e. called Wide Area Network (WAN) for example:

Figure 4.4

4.2.2 THE SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

In order to carry out a the characteristics and advantages of computerizing the stock exchange system there are software or packaging (application) which will enhance and improve the management of the stock exchange. There are numerous of the software available but individual company or country chooses the approached area of interest.

These package include

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- i. ICC share watch (on-line data base)
- ii. Exchange's Topic: this provides information or current price.
- iii. Data stream
- iv. Citiserver
- v. ICC direct and ICC key notes
- vi. MEAL (Medal Expenditure Analysis Ltd)
- vii. MINTEL

All the above listed are called on – line database the alternation methods of obtaining current business information include the use of CD - ROM to provide a regular updates on financial whether by communication links or the use of CD – ROM. The majority of this database involves subscription charge paying a subscription would provide the user with relevant passwords allowing access into database. The use of such information services has increased dramatically in recent years. The use of such information services has increased dramatically in recent years. This is due to a number of factors of including improvement on technology and communication system.

4.3 DOCUMENTATION

It is an interesting to describe how the system is developed and how it is being documented, implemented and maintained.

System documentation deals with how the newly design system is properly documented, including the guides ion file, computer printed result and further procedures for the user of the new system. In the documentation of the forms used for the system as a whole is described thoroughly by enumerating the forms used for the system requirement for the successful implementation of the system and the procedures from input and output.

Documentation involves the detailed description of each of the program that makes up the entire system; the system is composed of the keyboard, central processing unit (CPU) and the visual display unit (VDU).

One of the most important aspects in the computerization of the stock exchange system is the program to process all basic of the system.

4.3.1 PROGRAM DOCUMENTATION

There are two categories of forms used in this application, they are: The Input and Output forms. The input forms are used to supply data and other necessary information into the system. The output forms are used to display information from the database. Input and Output data are kept in the database for easy accessibility and security.

4.3.2 OPERATING THE SYSTEM

After booting the system, insert the CD that contains the program applications into the CD-ROM drive and select the file named Stock Exchange, the program will request for password and after the password is supplied, the user can select or check for staff registration, brokers registration, subscriber, stock, daily summary and report on the desktop screen, the user will be automatically taken to the program environment. The user can then perform necessary task on the program.

4.3.3 MAINTAINING THE SYSTEM

The maintenance of this application like other applications can be made suitable. By the use, this will involve frequent watch out for redundancy in the program coupled with any addition needed.

The program application can be changed or modified to facilitate system whereby the program can be accessed from different departments in the organization.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

5.1 SUMMARY

In the case study, we have extensively dealt with the stock exchange with an environment considerable to Nigeria standard policies and procedures of stock exchange market.

The major highlight of the findings include the generation of a standard format for retrieving, updating, storing and compilation of records in the computerized stock exchange system and obtaining and obtaining the processed results.

All the programs have been developing with user (for better understanding) and they have been properly documented in Visual basic language.

5.2 EXPERIENCED GAINED

A lot of experienced as being gained in the completion of this project most especially, this project enlightened more on the activities of the stock exchange, such as their mode of operations, the technical terms used, aims of stock exchange and the benefits from the stock exchanges.

Another aspect which is very important is the implementation computer carrying out some duties of using normal ways.

To conclude it all, an experienced as gained in the program coding and flowchart. Its way of advancing oneself writing a comprehensive program.

5.3 CONCLUSION

The problems of a market stock exchange have been solved by creating computer based with programs written and completed to meet the desired objectives and satisfactory results that would further improve the services and management of the stock exchange system in Nigeria.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION

The present set up of the stock exchange system lacks adequate resorting, documentation and information dissemination to carry out segregation of duty i.e. proper checking on the day transaction of securities (stocks, bonds and shares). Hence, the first growing of the system is been computerized because of the importance and characteristics, if computer and the impact has made in the 20th century; future advantage in next millennium which is almost going to be continuous revolution in every sphere of human endeavor.

The use of computerized system in each stock exchange market will enhance accuracy of results, speeds, of processing, reliability of transactions etc.

REFERENCES

- Adefioye Onaolapo Akerele (1998). *Efficiency of the Nigerian Securities Market* (PDF). Retrieved 2011-06-08
- Alile, H. I. and Anao, R. A (1990). *The Nigerian Stock Exchange in Operation*. Lagos Academic Press.
- Alufe F (2005). *A Review of Nigerian Capital Market. A Year of Mega offers*. Financial Standard.
- Bryon goitred schaum's. *Computer communication 3rd edition*
- Diamond, Peter A. (1967). "The Role of a stock Market in a General Equilibrium Model with Technological Uncertainty"
- French C.S computer science. *An instructional manual. data processing publishing*, 1980
- Frank J. Fabozzi, Steve V. Mam, Moorad Choudhry. *The global money markets* wiley and Finance, Wily and sons (2002)
- Lemke and lins, *Soft Dollars and Other Trading Activities*, \$2:3 (Thomson West, 2013 – 2014 ed.).
- Mala, R. and M Reddy, (2007). *Measuring Stock Market volatility in an emerging economy*. Int. Res. J. Fin. Eco., 8:126-133
- Olowe, R.A, (1999). *Weak from efficiency of the Nigerian Stock Market further evidence*. Afr. Dev. Rev., 11:54-68
- Oderinde Kehinde Rachael

Salisu, A.A. (2012). "Option pricing under stochastic volatility models for the Nigerian Stock Market". *The Empirical Economics Letters*, 11(2)

Sere-Ejembi, A.A. (2008). "Nigerian Stock Market Reflection of the Global Financial Crisis: An Evaluation". *Central Bank of Nigeria Bullion*. Vol. 32, no 4, pp. 4-11

The stock Exchange. Nigerian Stock Exchange. Retrieved 2012-06-08

The Nigeria Stock Exchange, (2007). *Comparative trading activities*. The annual Report and Accounts pp:34

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FLOWCHART PASSWORD

MAIN MENU

CLIENT

COMPANY PROFILE

REPORT

PROGRAM INTERFACE (VISUAL BASIC)

LOGIN

CLIENT PROFILE CREATION

WELCOME TO STOCKARAGE [Client Profile]

THE Nigerian STOCK EXCHANGE *Live from the Trading Floor*

Client Profile Creation

Clients Name:
Address:
Phone No: **Sex:**
Issuing Company:
Stock Type: **Unit Bought:**
Unit Price: **Total Worth:** N/A
Transaction Date:
Passport:

DESIGNED BY GROUP 113: SUPERVISED BY: MR MURITALA

THE Nigerian STOCK EXCHANGE *Client Profile REPORT*
Live from the Trading Floor

Client Name	Address	Sex	Company	Stock Type	Unit Bought	Total
ayinde ruqayat	poly gate	Male	firstown ventures	Shared	2	20
Olagunju Moses Tayo	Ara	Male	COnerstone venture	Stocks	4	80
Oderinde Kenny Rachael	Adejumobi	Female	Prime venture	Stocks	4	0
Oloruntoba Samson Segun	No 12 Aduralere Street	Male	Coca Cola B	Shared	3000	17400
Oloruntoba Samson S.	No 12 Aduralere Street	Male	Coca Cola B	Shared	3000	17400

COMPANY PROFILE CREATION

WELCOME TO STOCK BROKERAGE [Company Profile]

THE Nigerian STOCK EXCHANGE *Live from the Trading Floor*

New Company Profile Creation

Company Name:

Issue/Offer Type: Total Offer:

Alloted Units: Unit Price:

Company Hotline:

Offer Open Date: Date & Time: **24-Jun-2015**

Offer Close Date: **08:19:36 PM**

DESIGNED BY GROUP 113: SUPERVISED BY:MR MURITALA .K.

THE Nigerian STOCK EXCHANGE *Company Profile REPORT*
Live from the Trading Floor

Company Name	Offer Type	Total Offer	Alloted Unit	Unit Price	Open Date	Close Date
Coca Cola Bolting Comapny	Shared	10000	65000	6.5	2-Mar-2012	5-Jul-2012
Ayo Phamacy Nig. Limited, Ilor	Stocks	56000	560000	6.97	2-Mar-2010	3-Mar-2012
Qudus Ali	Shared	40000	600000	6.2	5-May-2010	4-Jun-2012
Ogunmoded Samson	Shared	20000	200000	2.6	9-Apr-2006	7-Jan-2011
Mohammed	Stocks	15000	150000	3.6	4-Nov-2008	28-Feb-2011